

Experimental and Mathematical Modelling of Conversion of Animal Fat Oil into Biodiesel Over Waste-Derived Hydroxy Sodalite in a Fixed-Bed Bioreactor

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Abstract

An experimental and mathematical modelling of conversion of animal fat oil (AFO) to biodiesel using waste-derived hydroxy sodalite (HSOD) catalyst in a fixed-bed reactor was conducted. A modified three step Eley-Rideal reaction model was employed and previous studies carried out using a batch reactor with AFO catalyzed by waste-derived HSOD provided some preliminary experimental and reaction kinetics data. A comparison of the kinetic performance of the batch and continuous fixed bed reactor (FBR) processes were investigated to further understand the overall conversion performance with the waste-derived HSOD catalyst. Experimental and mathematical modelling results reveal that the FBR feed rate should be faster than 0.4 ml min⁻¹ in order to overcome external diffusion limitations. The results indicated that as the diameter of the catalyst particles remain lower than 0.19 mm, the effect of internal diffusion mass transfer difficulties was overcome based on simplifying model assumption. It was also identified that an Eley-Rideal mechanism model was able to describe the kinetic performance of the transesterification in a fixed bed reactor and the system surface reaction of triglyceride with adsorbed methanol assumed to be the rate-determining step (RDS). The kinetics of the transesterification catalysed by waste-derived HSOD in a fixed bed reactor fitted well with the experimental data and in agreement with the literature. From the comparison of the batch and FBR, it was observed that the waste-derived HSOD displayed higher catalytic activity (higher conversion) in the transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME in the FBR than in the batch reactor.

Keywords Mathematical Modelling; Kinetic Reaction; Hydroxy Sodalite; Heterogeneous Catalyst; Fixed Bed Reactor; Biodiesel

Citation Aniokete, T. C., Aniaku, V. O. Daramola, M. O. (2023). Experimental and Mathematical Modelling of Conversion of Animal Fat Oil into Biodiesel Over Waste-Derived Hydroxy Sodalite in a Fixed-Bed Bioreactor. *American Journal of Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 4(1), 50-62. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8248527>

Introduction

The role of biodiesel production in the energy equation of South Africa has been extensively discussed earlier in our previous works especially fuel production from the abundant waste materials. However, biodiesel production in terms of South African energy revolution is, therefore, incomplete without input from conversion of waste AFO into the 20 % renewable fuel (biodiesel) energy mix (Nolte, 2007) which steadily has attracted a great research interest founded on the following four curious points:

- i. The heavily polluting fossil fuel reserve (coal resource), steadily depletes, coupled with growing concern for CO₂ emission and associated climate change constitute concerns for the search for other renewable feedstocks for sustainable fuel including biodiesel which has many advantages
- ii. Selective molecular transformations in chemical manufacturing industries including biodiesel are encouraged by government in the utilization of catalysts such as novel heterogeneous waste-derived HSOD catalyst
- iii. Disposal of waste animal fat oil (AFO) from the abattoirs into the open landfills globally constitute huge environmental concern until benefited for biodiesel production as value added
- iv. Utilizing novel heterogeneous catalysts, for example, will crucially overcome the scientific and engineering drawbacks of the conventional catalysts to economically feasible biodiesel production

In this study, modelling of a waste-derived solid HSOD catalyst fixed bed reactor (FBR) for AFO biodiesel production could be instrumental to understanding the transesterification process in this direction. The literature review done in this study highlighted the findings obtained from batch, semi-batch and continuous stirred tank reactors (CSTR) (Likozar and Levec, 2014; Haigh et al., 2014; Brásio et al., 2013). However, there is limited or no information on the fixed bed reactor (FBR) for continuous conversion of waste animal fat oil (AFO) to biodiesel over solid HSOD waste-derived catalyst. This information is useful to ensure effective and sustainable biodiesel production in South Africa and around the globe.

Fixed bed reactor has been used in different chemical engineering processes, and it can assume different designs and shapes depending on the process that is considered. For example, a uniformly catalytic particles secured in a defined space in a reactor for chemical species' contacting is termed a fixed/packed bed reactor. In this reactor, the particles are randomly arranged but are fixed in position. Reactant mixture flows through the pore/void spaces in the catalyst particle bed. The flow mechanism is such that the reactant molecules are carried initially from the bulk stream fluid to the catalyst surface, and next via the catalyst pores/voids. Inside the catalyst voids, adsorption takes place on the pores thereby resulting in chemical reaction or transformation. The resultant products of the chemical transformation within the catalyst pore spaces further desorb into the bulk stream fluid. This flow phenomenon is thus, inherently characterized by one of the mechanisms of fluid transport systems such as convection. In convective transport phenomena, heat and mass transport of reactive particles are eminent. The transport of heat and mass of reactive particles are crucial to the yield and quality of transesterification products at any instant in fixed bed reactor (FBR) system employed in this study. Therefore, the distribution of mass of reactive particle species and the heat flow is a complicated one due to the development of web of flow patterns from the catalyst packing (spherical glass beads). In addition to this, there arises the issues of problematic diffusion of molecules, direct thermal conductive flow and flows due to solid phases and radiations. All the same, the generation or utilization of heat is encountered in most chemical reaction systems such as waste-derived solid HSOD catalytic FBR transesterification of AFO to biodiesel. The excess production of heat in this case is usually removed or supplied through various process schemes including tube walls of reactors. As stated before, the physical and chemical transformations occurring in FBRs are complicated, pointing directly to the fact that their exact description could be impossible or one of a difficult mathematical expatiation. The precise meaning of this is that a detailed mathematical model requires an exact list of parameters for its description. Conversely, a few details to the studied model implies inadequate mathematical model. However, it is very noteworthy to involve the most effective measurable parameters of the elementary processes of the system. This will forestall lack of accurate parameter estimation. One best approach to avoid this is through the reliance on model simplification. Model simplification captures the most relevant and representative elements of the problem. It is necessary to assert that in mathematical model building, there is 'no universal model'. This implies that there is 'no worst or best' model either. Further, the 'best' model could be chosen based on the particular circumstances of the system being addressed. In addition, it depends on the model as well as the possibility

of obtaining a successful mathematical treatment of the model equations. Several classes of numerical models for studying FBR had been applied (Wehinger et al., 2015; Aksikas et al., 2009). Typical of such is the application of theory of continuum models. Continuum process models possess heterogeneous systems in which there are one or more phases. The particular treatments given to the continuum results in a set of differential or algebraic expressions for the bulk fluid and solid phase variables (Damköhler, 1936; Hlavacek et al., 1976; Froment and Bischoff, 1977).

The other approach considers the particles of the catalyst and the bulk fluid as a reactor unit. The catalyst and the bulk fluid contact each other and other units. Interactions between them take place forming a network. A model based on this unit or cell is considered as a cell model (Deans and Lapidus, 1960; McGuire and Lapidus, 1965; Vanderveen et al., 1968; Hlavacek et al., 1976). Generally referred to as the classical continuum model or channel model, the cell model's transport processes take into consideration the various interactions of the cells and their adjoining cells and the type of model of interest. Some set of classical continuum mathematical models incorporate experimentally determined description of the porosity distribution of the particles. These further exhibits maximal porosity close to the wall with decreasing porosity outwards in the axial direction. This usually presents an oscillatory trajectory with a period of 1-2 particle diameters. However, after a period of 4-5 particle diameters, the effect of the wall on the local porosity disappears.

Depending on the configuration of the FBR, channelling models are developed assuming the catalyst bed to be separated by co-axial cylindrical surfaces passing through the free volume and reaching its minimal values. These surfaces divide the reactor into a set of co-axial annular channels, thereby tending to a plug flow reactor status. Consequently, the fluid velocity is determined by the average porosity of the channel exchanging heat and mass transfer with the adjoining channels. Therefore, from the aforementioned, channel models can be considered as generalization of the classical continuum models. This implies that the merits and demerits of the classical continuum models have as a matter of fact been acquired by channel models. Though, each mathematical model has its potential merits and demerits, the most common model used in FBR is continuum models (Donaubauer et al., 2019; Stegehake et al., 2019; Moghaddam et al., 2019). The apparent popularity of continuum models in FBR modelling is linked with the fact that mass and heat transfer experiments earlier described were adequately analysed using the continuum models. In addition, parameter estimation was exact and sufficient. Furthermore, the non-linearity of reaction rates associated with some processes are better treated using differential equations when compared with using algebraic expressions. However, advanced numerical techniques are increasingly being explored in obtaining solutions of non-linear differential and algebraic equations associated with FBR modelling problems.

Some authors including (Singh and Fernando, 2007, Singh and Fernando, 2009) have carried out transesterification of oil into biodiesel in a batch reactor using heterogeneous catalysts of metal oxides including MgO, CaO, BaO, PbO, MnO₂ and Na -based mixed metal oxides. The kinetic parameters such as the rate constants and reaction order were compared. The works of the authors were quite interesting. Also, in a different study carried out by the (Huang et al., 2009) for the transesterification of crude soybean oil with methanol catalyzed by Mg (OCH₃)₂, the result obtained was attractive, but unfortunately, the authors considered only batch process for the biodiesel production. A continuous fixed bed reactor flow for biodiesel production will minimize the over-dependency on fossil fuels for energy generation. It will also create energy efficiency and sustainability, but understanding the process requires several experiments which alternatively could be circumvented via process modelling.

The development of mathematical model of a fixed bed reactor flow is crucial for the description of the biodiesel conversion process and in some cases, for understanding the behavior of the system based on the physical and chemical phenomena occurring in the process (Freund et al., 2003). In this case, the static and dynamic behaviour for process design, optimization and control via dynamic simulation of the system (Khanna and Seinfeld 1987) are considered.. For industrially relevant applications, FBR has been used for large scale processing in the petroleum industry, for instance, in catalytic reforming and hydro-treatments (Iordanidis 2002). This work presents the mathematical modelling of an FBR to gain knowledge of the behaviour and performance of waste-derived solid HSOD catalyst during the transesterification of AFO in the reactor and compare the performance to that of a batch reactor. The study explores among other issues accounting for the heat and mass transfer limitations due to the heterogeneous nature of AFO transesterification process and modelling considered reaction kinetics via the

interaction of the fluid with the waste-derived HSOD catalyst. The result of this modelling was validated with experimental data.

Experimental

Materials

The major materials used for the catalysts synthesis and biodiesel production are CFA, WIB, AFO, and others and the methods used for each of the process had been described in the methodology section in our published works (Aniokete et al., 2019a; Aniokete et al., 2019b).

Experimental Setup/Facility

Figure1 displays an FBR flow configuration consisting of a fixed bed of HSOD waste-derived catalyst for the conversion of AFO to biodiesel in a continuous mode. The feed (methanol and AFO) heated to a known value close to the reaction temperature was delivered into the reactor under pressurized pumping (Watson Marlow 313S peristaltic pump) at a fixed flow rate. The feed mixture which axially percolates through the catalyst bed was supported with spherical glass beads, made of sintered glass with pores at both ends. The reaction temperature was regulated using a glass jacketed system. The mechanism of heating fluid entering and exiting ensures uniform temperature in the reactor. The flow of the reactant mixture in the bed was in an axial direction, ensured contact and occurrence of chemical reaction amongst the reacting species. The product formed during the process is collected through the product outlet. There is mass and heat transfer as the reacting mixture flows down the bed. Furthermore, the concentration of the species varies along the bed based on the reaction conditions. The process being a continuous type, provided the basic advantages over a batch reactor such as effective mixing and conversion. Table 1 shows the operating conditions used for the transesterification process.

Figure 1: Schematic process flow diagram for conversion of AFO to biodiesel over waste-derived HSOD in a fixed-bed reactor (FBR).

Table 1: Process reaction condition obtained from (Aniokete et al., 2019a; Aniokete et al., 2019b)

Process parameter	Set condition
Methanol-to-AFO molar ratio	10:1
Catalyst amount (%)	2.5
Reaction temperature (°C)	40-65
Reaction time (min)	120

Model Development and Formulation

In this study, the model is developed based on the kinetic theories and controlling segments proposed by (Xiao et al., 2010), but the model was slightly modified with respect to the following three conditions:

- i. A mass transfer-controlled region at the internal surface of the heterogeneous catalyst
- ii. An irreversible chemical reaction-controlled region at the pseudo-homogeneous fluid body, and
- iii. A reversible equilibrium chemical reaction-controlled region close to the transesterification equilibrium stage.

Still on the FBR modelling, (Dossin et al., 2006b), investigated the transesterification of ethyl acetate with methanol over magnesium oxide as the solid base catalyst. Their intrinsic kinetic model was based on Eley-Rideal three-step mechanism. This was proposed in line with the experimental data from a perfectly mixed slurry batch reactor system. It was their opinion that transesterification took place between the methanol adsorbed on solid base free sites and the ethyl acetate from the liquid phase. The Eley-Rideal three-step mechanism include:

- i. Methanol adsorption
- ii. Surface reaction, and
- iii. Ethanol adsorption.

According to Dossin et al. (Dossin et al., 2006b) methanol adsorption was considered as the rate determining step (RDS) being the slowest reaction step. Shortly after, these authors (Dossin et al., 2006a) further applied the Eley-Rideal three-step mechanism on the transesterification of triolein with methanol to methyl oleate and was used to simulate the continuous production of biodiesel from rapeseed oil. Also, Ca-based solid base was studied in a continuous biodiesel production in a fixed bed reactor (Hsieh et al., 2010). Importantly, a Langmuir-Hinshelwood (LH) model of transesterification was established according to the experimental data. The overall reaction was described as the adsorption of methanol and vegetable oil, a series of surface reactions, and desorption of FAME and glycerol. One of the surface reactions was assumed to be rate-determining. The transesterification of vegetable oil and methanol through solid base involves three-phase liquid-liquid-solid heterogeneous reaction. The overall reaction process consists of the intrinsic reaction, inter-liquid mass transfer, and liquid-solid external and internal mass transfers. It was established by another set of researchers that a heterogeneous liquid-liquid-solid model was studied based on liquid-solid external model in the transesterification of soybean oil to biodiesel with methanol using solid base catalysts (Liu et al., 2010). This study considered pseudo-first order kinetic reaction for the transesterification activity. The intrinsic kinetics was considered using a huge molar excess of methanol. To the best of our knowledge, however, no intrinsic kinetic models of transesterification of AFO and methanol catalysed by solid base hydroxy sodalite catalyst in a fixed bed reactor has been reported.

Results and Discussion

Reaction Model Development and Formulation

In this study, a three-step Eley-Rideal model was employed to describe the catalytic transesterification of AFO to biodiesel with methanol. In our previous study, the overall kinetic reaction was represented by $TG + 3M \leftrightarrow 3F + G$; where M is methanol. For model development and formulation, the transesterification process model is represented by the three elementary steps depicted in Equations (1) to (3), respectively.

where **TG** is the triglyceride AFO, **A**, the alcohol (methanol), **DG** is diglyceride, **ME** is the methyl ester, **MG** is monoglyceride, and **GL** represents glycerol. Equations (1), (2) and (3), designate the three-step mechanisms of the Eley-Rideal reaction model

Similarly, the intrinsic kinetic model of the transesterification reaction is shown in Equation (4):

Where **TG** is the triglyceride AFO, **M** is methanol, **F** is the AFOFAME and **G** is the glycerol.

The reaction rate of the transesterification reaction catalyzed by solid base HSOD can be written as Equation (5):

$$r_p = -\frac{dF_p}{dW} = -\frac{dF_{po}(1-x)}{dW} = \frac{F_{po} dx}{dW} = \frac{dx}{d(W/F_{po})} \quad (5)$$

Where **W** is weight of solid catalyst, **V** is the volumetric flow rate of feed.

For the accurate mathematical modelling of an FBR which is a continuous flow operation, the kinetic reaction experiments were carried out by assuming a plug flow pattern. This is a steady state plug flow reaction and was considered on the basis that the concentration varies along the length of the tubular reactor in the axial direction. Table 2 shows the details of the physical parameters of the reactor. The universal gas constant R, and the operating pressure P, were obtained from standard state; the density ρ_{cat} , was calculated, and surface area of the catalyst A, was obtained via characterization. The length L, and radius R_1 , of the FBR were measured.

Table 2: Physical parameters of the FBR proposed for this study

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Universal gas constant (Jmol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	R	8.314
Operating pressure (Pa)	P	101325
Density of waste-derived HSOD (Kgm ⁻³)	ρ_{cat}	28.87
Length of FBR (m)	L	0.15
Radius of FBR (m)	R_1	1.1×10^{-2}
Surface area of waste-derived HSOD catalyst (m ² g ⁻¹)	A	31.00

Reactor Model

In this study, the limitations of mass transfer effects were removed before measuring the intrinsic kinetic data. The transesterification procedure which has been described earlier was catalysed by the waste-derived HSOD followed by the three mass transfer processes namely;

- i. Mass transfer on the liquid-liquid interface of methanol to AFO
- ii. External diffusion of the methanol and oil phase into the waste-derived HSOD (liquid-solid) catalyst and
- iii. Internal diffusion of the waste-derived HSOD catalyst into the bulk fluid (solid-liquid; desorption)

It must be stressed at this point that there are no liquid-liquid mass transfer limitations assumed for this system. This implies that interliquid mass transfer, liquid-solid external and internal mass transfer limitations are eliminated. The intrinsic kinetic model of the transesterification between AFO and methanol catalysed by waste-derived HSOD

was pursued according to experimental data obtained in a fixed bed reactor. The model is based on the Eley-Rideal three-step mechanism and this indicates a new mechanism of transesterification catalysed by solid base.

Figure 2: Sectional view of fixed bed reactor model packed with solid HSOD waste-derived catalyst particles

Figure 2 is a cross-section of the fixed bed reactor (FBR) model undergoing heterogeneous catalytic transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME (fatty acid methyl ester from animal fat oil) with methanol as the alcohol. The feed stream consists of AFO and methanol which is driven into the catalyst bed as shown. The feed stream moves through the fixed bed fully contacted with the catalyst. Chemical reaction takes place and the reaction product is withdrawn from the reactor through the exit for analysis. This section focuses on investigating the kinetic behaviour and performance of waste-derived HSOD on the transesterification of AFO to biodiesel in a fixed bed reactor. The performance of this catalyst in the FBR was compared with that of a batch reactor using Eley-Rideal mechanism. The standard reaction schemes for this process have been presented and explained including the rate Equation (5). The conversion occurred from point to point in the reactor, while the modelling steps account for the happenings as detailed subsequently.

In this study, the “reaction holding time” was defined as the catalyst weight, \mathbf{W} over the volumetric feed rate \mathbf{V} . The reaction holding time, therefore, is (\mathbf{W}/\mathbf{V}) . In the experiments, the catalyst weight was increased proportionally with the increase of the volume feed rate to achieve a stable feed flow rate over the same reaction time. The holding time, therefore, could be made to remain constant by (\mathbf{W}/\mathbf{V}) , implying that these reactions were carried out at the same reaction time. Being focused on this, we did not consider varying the volume feed rate and transient effect on contact time with the catalyst as well as the superficial velocity of the reactant. At constant holding time, the conversion of the reactant did not change with the feed rates, necessitating that the liquid-solid external diffusion mass transfer resistances could be ignored completely. Figure 3. depicts the conversion of the same holding time with different feed rates.

Figure 3: Liquid-solid external diffusion effects at 60 °C (333K), $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10:1$, $W/V = 3.4321$, $g \text{ min mL}^{-1}$.

To overcome the problem of external diffusion limitations, the feed rate should be controlled faster than 0.4 mL min^{-1} . However, as the conversion of the reactant did not change with the diameter of the catalyst particles, the liquid-solid internal diffusion mass-transfer resistances are neglected as well. Results of Table 3. indicate that when the diameter of the catalyst was not larger than 0.19 mm whereby the conversions remained constant and therefore, the internal diffusion limitations were ignored.

Table 3: Liquid-solid internal diffusion mass-transfer effects at 60 °C (333K), $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10:1$, $W = 4g$, $V = 0.88 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$

D_p (mm)	0.93-0.39	0.39-0.26	0.26-0.0.19	0.19-0.16	< 0.13
X (%)	63.45	95.1	97.84	98.64	98.93

The Table indicates that at various particle diameters (pores or voids) of catalyst, it is feasible to estimate feed conversion rate at specified reaction temperature, flow rate, catalyst weight and volume flow rate. At various experimental points, the Table 4 was generated in a MATLAB solver.

Table 4: Intrinsic kinetic data and estimation of reaction rates at 60 °C (333K), $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10:1$, $W = 4g$

V (ml mol^{-1})	$F_{po} \times 10^{-3}$ (mol min^{-1})	$W/F_{po} \times 10^3$ (mol min^{-1})	(Fractional conversion) x	$dx/d\left(\frac{W}{F_{po}}\right) \times 10^{-3}$ ($\text{mol min}^{-1} g^{-1}$)
-	-	-	0	0.4213
4.9800	1.8577	1.4948	0.4892	0.2245
2.9800	1.4286	2.0291	0.6382	0.1375
2.0800	0.8951	2.8463	0.8624	0.0647
1.7800	0.6324	3.2869	0.8851	0.0072
1.4800	0.4121	4.6312	0.8911	0.0061
0.8800	0.3111	7.8212	0.8768	0.0056

Eley-Rideal model was used to derive the rate equation for the transesterification of AFO and methanol in the FBR. From this model, the three steps of the process namely the adsorption of methanol, series of surface reactions of methanol adsorption with glyceride from the liquid phase, and the desorption of the glycerol.

Figure 5: Experimental data and model estimated fit for the kinetics at 60 °C (333K), $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10:1$, $W = 4\text{g}$.

As seen in Equation (4), the overall reaction has been explained and shows the formation of AFOFAME denoted by F and glycerol by G. For the elemental steps, Equations (6) to Equation (10) were used.

$$r_p = \frac{K \left(C_{TG} C_A - \frac{1}{K} \frac{C_F^3 C_G}{C_A^2} \right)}{1 + K_A C_A + K_G C_G} \quad (11)$$

The desorption of the glycerol from the active sites of the catalyst takes place at this point and ∂ denotes the void space of the catalyst. As surface reaction is assumed to be rate-determining (Hattori et al., 2000), since in this case a base is catalysing the reaction. Also, (Noureddini and Zhu, 1997) had proven that reaction of triglyceride with methanol was slower than those of di- and monoglycerides.

The regression model carried out for the conversion process is presented in Table 5.

Table.5: Kinetic parameters obtained at different temperatures given $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10 :1$, $W = 4\text{g}$, $V = 0.88 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

Reaction temperature T (K)	Rate constant K ($\text{L}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$)	Reaction equilibrium constant K^*	Adsorption equilibrium constant K_b (Lmol^{-1})	Desorption equilibrium constant K_d (Lmol^{-1})	Conversion X (%)
313	0.0129	0.052	1.46	5.86	22.23
318	0.0146	0.069	1.23	4.53	56.42
323	0.0168	0.094	0.99	3.72	81.15
328	0.0194	0.180	0.87	2.51	98.83
333	0.0248	0.327	0.61	1.23	98.82
338	0.0312	0.422	0.51	0.82	98.16

Under this condition, Equation (7) is regarded as the rate-determining step (RDS), and the other steps (i.e., Equation (6, 8, 9 and 10) regarded as being in equilibrium states. After a reasonable procedure, Equation (11) was derived to represent the overall rate equation.

At this point, a multiple non-linear regression was applied to estimate the four kinetic parameters including k , K , K_b and K_d that were used for the model development. It is shown in Table 5. Figure 6 indicates that model computation agreed well with the experimental data, implying that Eley-Rideal model mechanism aptly describes the kinetics of the transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME with methanol and catalysed by waste-derived HSOD in a fixed bed reactor.

Table 5 shows the regressed results of model parameters of the experiments. The rate constants increased with increasing temperature, thereby obeying the Arrhenius law (Xiao et al., 2010). Reaction equilibrium constant equally increased with temperature and this has a positive implication that the transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME with methanol is an endothermic reaction.

Figure 6: Regression model for rate constants

This observation agrees with the literature (Hsieh et al., 2010, Aniokete et al., 2019). Within the temperature range investigated, the kinetics obeyed the Arrhenius law:

$$K = Ae^{-E_a/RT} \quad (12)$$

$$\ln K = \ln A + \left[-\frac{E_a}{R}\right] \frac{1}{T} \quad (13)$$

In estimating Arrhenius model parameters, linear regression was used.

Figure 6 is linear relationship for $\ln K$ and $1/K$ using Equation (13) showing a perfect fit of the model. The correlation determination (COD)/coefficient of determination of the plot was found to be 0.97751, while the activation energy obtained was 30,903.30 Jmol⁻¹. It can be stated that as the temperature of the reaction increased significantly, the conversion of the reaction increased, up to certain point in the presence of the waste-derived HSOD. This is evidenced by the fact that when the reaction temperature was 313K, the conversion was 22.23 % and the temperature reached 333K, the conversion could reach 98.82%. This suggests that temperature played a key role in the transesterification on both kinetic and thermodynamic considerations. It can be observed that K_b and K_d values, which are the adsorption equilibrium constants decreased with the increase of temperature as a result of the exothermic adsorption process of the reaction. Furthermore, all adsorption equilibrium constants of methanol at different temperatures of the reaction were less than that of the glycerol and could be explained by the fact that the hydroxyl value of methanol was smaller (Xiao et al., 2010).

Model validation with experimental data

The developed model was verified via the experimental data obtained from biodiesel conversion and is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Model verification based on $C_{po} = 0.4517 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $m = 10:1$, $W = 4\text{g}$, $V = 0.88 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$

Molar ratio of methanol-to-AFO	4:1	6:1	8:1	10:1	12:1	14:1
Model product conversion (%)	20.95	57.12	82.23	97.86	96.97	97.75
Experimental data (%)	22.23	56.42	81.15	98.83	98.82	98.16

Table 6. shows the model computation and the experimental data for the conversion at different molar ratios of methanol-to-AFO. The values are compared to each other. It could be seen that the deviation from both experimental and the model data are negligibly lower than 10 %, which suggests that the kinetic model can well predict conversion of transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME catalysed by waste-derived HSOD within a certain range.

The kinetic parameters and data obtained during catalytic transesterification by waste-derived HSOD with methanol of AFO to AFOFAME under well-mixed batch and continuous flow fixed bed reactor (FBR) are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: FBR Model Data compared with Batch Kinetic Data

Parameter	Batch reactor	Fixed bed reactor	Variance factor (%)
Reaction order	1st	1st	-
Rate constant (min ⁻¹) at 328K	0.0177	0.0194	4.58
Activation energy, E_a (Jmol ⁻¹)	31473.65	30903.30	0.92
Pre-exponential constant A_o (min ⁻¹)	7.56	7.46 ± 0.866	4.82 ± 2.00
Conversion (%)	97.84	98.83	0.5
Regression coefficient	0.98293	0.97751	0.27

The variance factor for the two reactors indicates significant performance for rate constant and pre-exponential constant (**A₀**) for the FBR and low performance for batch reactor. The low activation energy, higher rate constant and pre-exponential factor for the FBR model implies that the waste-derived HSOD catalyst efficiently converted AFO to AFOFAME.

Conclusion

An experimental and mathematical modelling of conversion of AFO into biodiesel over waste-derived HSOD in a fixed-bed reactor was studied using experimental data and kinetic data obtained from transesterification of AFO to biodiesel. A modified three step Eley-Rideal reaction model proposed by (Xiao et al., 2010) was employed. The following conclusions were made:

- i. To overcome the external diffusion limitations, the feed rate should be faster than 0.4 mL min⁻¹.
- ii. As the diameter of the catalyst particles remain lower than 0.19 mm, the effect of internal diffusion mass transfer difficulties was overcome based on simplifying model assumption.
- iii. With the mass transfer issues addressed, an Eley-Rideal mechanism model was able to describe the kinetic performance of the transesterification in a fixed bed reactor and the system surface reaction of triglyceride with adsorbed methanol was assumed to be the rate-determining step (RDS).
- iv. The kinetics of the transesterification catalysed by waste-derived HSOD in a fixed bed reactor fitted well with the experimental data and in agreement with the literature.
- v. From the comparison of the batch and FBR, it was observed that the waste-derived HSOD displayed higher catalytic activity (higher conversion) in the transesterification of AFO to AFOFAME in the FBR than in the batch reactor.

However, the intrinsic kinetic model described in this study is recommended to further to gain more understanding of the transesterification reaction catalyzed by the novel solid base waste-derived HSOD as an industrial catalyst.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses deep gratitude to WITS MMU unit and their tutorial staff for the analytical facilities provided during the course of this research.

References

- Aksikas, I., Fuxman, A., Forbes, J.F., Winkin, J.J., (2009). LQ control design of a class of hyperbolic PDE systems: Application to fixed-bed reactor. *Automatica* 45, 1542–1548.
- Aniokete, T., Ozonoh, M., Daramola, M.O., 2019. Synthesis of Pure and High Surface Area Sodalite Catalyst from Waste Industrial Brine and Coal Fly Ash for Conversion of Waste Cooking Oil (WCO) to Biodiesel. *Int. J. Renew. Energy Res. IJERER* 9, 1924–1937.
- Aniokete, T.C., Mbhele, S., Mdlalani, V., Ozonoh, M., Daramola, M.O., (2019). Kinetic Study of Waste-derived Solid Hydroxy Sodalite Catalyst during Transesterification of Animal Fat Oil to Biodiesel in a Batch Reactor. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 1378, 032081.
- Brásio, A.S.R., Romanenko, A., Leal, J., Santos, L.O., Fernandes, N.C.P., (2013). Nonlinear model predictive control of biodiesel production via transesterification of used vegetable oils. *J. Process Control* 23, 1471–1479.
- Damköhler, G., (1936). Einflüsse der Strömung, Diffusion und des Wärmeüberganges auf die Leistung von Reaktionsöfen.: I. Allgemeine Gesichtspunkte für die Übertragung eines chemischen Prozesses aus dem Kleinen ins Große [WWW Document]. *Z. Für Elektrochem. Angew. Phys. Chem.* URL
- Deans, H.A., Lapidus, L., (1960). A computational model for predicting and correlating the behavior of fixed-bed reactors: I. Derivation of model for nonreactive systems. *AIChE J.* 6, 656–663.
- Donaubauer, P.J., Schmalhorst, L., Hinrichsen, O., (2019). 2D flow fields in fixed-bed reactor design: *a robust methodology for continuum models.* *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 208, 115137.
- Dossin, T.F., Reyniers, M.-F., Berger, R.J., Marin, G.B., (2006a). Simulation of heterogeneously MgO-catalyzed transesterification for fine-chemical and biodiesel industrial production. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 67, 136–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2006.04.008>
- Dossin, T.F., Reyniers, M.-F., Marin, G.B., (2006b). Kinetics of heterogeneously MgO-catalyzed transesterification. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 62, 35–45.

- Freund, H., Zeiser, T., Huber, F., Klemm, E., Brenner, G., Durst, F., Emig, G., (2003). Numerical simulations of single-phase reacting flows in randomly packed fixed-bed reactors and experimental validation. *Chem. Eng. Sci., 17th International Symposium of Chemical Reaction Engineering (IS CRE 17)* 58, 903–910.
- Froment, G.F., Bischoff, K.B., (1977). *Chemical Reactor Analysis and Design*. John Wiley & Sons, New York Chichester Brisbane Toronto.
- Haigh, K.F., Vladislavljević, G.T., Reynolds, J.C., Nagy, Z., Saha, B., (2014). Kinetics of the pre-treatment of used cooking oil using Novozyme 435 for biodiesel production. *Chem. Eng. Res. Des., ECCE9– 9th European Congress of Chemical Engineering 92*, 713–719.
- Hattori, H., Shima, M., Kabashima, H., (2000). Alcoholysis of ester and epoxide catalyzed by solid bases. *Stud. Surf. Sci. Catal.* 13, 3507–3512.
- Hlavacek, V., Hlavacek, V., Votruba, J., (1976). Steady State Operation of Fixed Bed Reactors and Monolithic Structures. *Steady State Oper. Fixed Bed React. Monolith. Struct.* 314.
- Hsieh, L.-S., Kumar, U., Wu, J.C.S., (2010). Continuous production of biodiesel in a packed-bed reactor using shell-core structural $\text{Ca}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{O}_3)_2/\text{CaCO}_3$ catalyst. *Chem. Eng. J.* 158, 250–256.
- Huang, K., Xu, Q.-L., Zhang, S.-P., Ren, Z.-W., Yan, Y.-J., (2009). Multi-Step Controlled Kinetics of the Transesterification of Crude Soybean Oil with Methanol by $\text{Mg}(\text{OCH}_3)_2$. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 32, 1595–1604.
- Iordanidis, A.A., (2002). *Mathematical Modeling of Catalytic Fixed Bed Reactors*. Twente University Press., P.O. Box 217, 7500 AE Enschede, The Netherlands.
- Khanna, R., Seinfeld, J.H., (1987). Mathematical modelling of packed bed reactors, in: *Advances in Chemical Engineering*. Academic Press, Pasadena, California, USA, pp. 113–189.
- Likozar, B., Levec, J., (2014). Transesterification of canola, palm, peanut, soybean and sunflower oil with methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, butanol and tert-butanol to biodiesel: Modelling of chemical equilibrium, reaction kinetics and mass transfer based on fatty acid composition. *Appl. Energy* 123, 108–120.
- Liu, X., Piao, X., Wang, Y., Zhu, S., (2010). Model Study on Transesterification of Soybean Oil to Biodiesel with Methanol Using Solid Base Catalyst. *J. Phys. Chem. A* 114, 3750–3755.
- McGuire, M.L., Lapidus, L., (1965). On the stability of a detailed packed-bed reactor. *AIChE J.* 11, 85–95. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690110120>
- Moghaddam, E.M., Foumeny, E.A., Stankiewicz, A.I., Padding, J.T., (2019). Fixed bed reactors of non-spherical pellets: Importance of heterogeneities and inadequacy of azimuthal averaging. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* X 1, 100006.
- Nolte, M., (2007). *Commercial biodiesel production in South Africa: a preliminary economic feasibility study* (Thesis). Stellenbosch: University of Stellenbosch.
- Noureddini, H., Zhu, D., (1997). Kinetics of transesterification of soybean oil. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.* 74, 1457–1463.
- Singh, A.K., Fernando, S.D., (2009). Preparation and Reaction Kinetics Studies of Na-based Mixed Metal Oxide for Transesterification. *Energy Fuels* 23, 5160–5164.
- Singh, A.K., Fernando, S.D., (2007). Reaction Kinetics of Soybean Oil Transesterification Using Heterogeneous Metal Oxide Catalysts. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 30, 1716–1720.
- Stegehake, C., Riese, J., Grünwald, M., (2019). Modelling and Validating Fixed-Bed Reactors: A State-of-the-Art Review. *ChemBioEng Rev.* 6, 28–44.
- Vanderveen, J.W., Luss, D., Amundson, N.R., (1968). Stability of adiabatic packed bed reactors. Effect of flow variations and coupling between the particles. *AIChE J.* 14, 636–643.
- Wehinger, G.D., Eppinger, T., Kraume, M., (2015). Detailed numerical simulations of catalytic fixed-bed reactors: Heterogeneous dry reforming of methane. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 122, 197–209.
- Xiao, Y., Gao, L., Xiao, G., Lv, J., (2010). Kinetics of the Transesterification Reaction Catalysed by Solid Base in a Fixed-Bed Reactor. *Energy Fuels* 24, 5829–5833.